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How is VET teacher's professionalism changing in work-based learning? An empirical research in some Italian schools on the model of school-work alternation

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Abstract

The paper reports an hypothetical framework for Vet teacher training in work-based learning within of my doctoral research.

The role of the teacher is becoming increasingly crucial for the student's learning in accompanying him in the school-work transitions. It is necessary, therefore that the teacher is more inclined to a role also of tutor able to activate in students a set of basic skills, technical and soft skills through the experience of learning at work in order to exercise an agency, in their own education and throughout life.

In Italy, this research area is still underdeveloped and therefore needs to be explored in comparison with the German-speaking countries where the dual learning paths are well structured.

Keywords

curriculum development; vet teachers; agency; situated learning; work-based learning

1 Introduction

The theme of VET teacher training is linked to some aspects of the work scenarios on which the pedagogy of work is based, questions including:

- The need to tackle the conditions that generate unemployment, especially youth unemployment (for example, the persistence of a significant proportion of young people in Neet (Not employment, not education or training));
- The need to improve education and vocational training not only as a "second or third choice" for the student;
- The transformation of work processes in progress against the "drivers" that emerge from the digitalisation of organizational processes in companies (Industry 4.0).

In Italy the situation of the Neet is not comforting and continues to increase, from 24% in 2005 to 33% in 2016. In Germany, on the other hand, where the dual system is well consolidated by Neet are continuously decreasing (20% in 2015 to 10% in 2016).

The causes of this continuous negative phenomenon in Italy are the consequence not only of the economic conjuncture triggered by the 2008 crisis, but we can identify the causes in particular in the structural distance between the educational system (school, University) and production systems (companies), already identifiable in the "first transitional phase" (secondary school).

The role of Vet teacher plays a key role in work based learning (WBL). We know how in the German-speaking countries (Germany, Austria, Switzerland, Denmark) where the dual system is consolidated, the teacher holds many roles, both as a teacher and as a tutor. In this perspective, it becomes above all a facilitator of the student's learning towards that process of school-work transition, a crucial step for the personal growth of the student.

In Italy, on the other hand the role of teacher especially in high schools, is still rooted in an exclusively didactic model. In the light, above all, of the ongoing legislative and cultural changes in the Italian vocational education and training system, a new impulse was given to the dual learning methodologies in initial training. In order to successfully train these paths, the teacher himself must begin to change his nature, his attitude towards a multidimensional nature, not only in a didactic key, but in a tutorship key, a guide in an perspective of learner's agency of student.

2 Research design

The doctoral research aims at analyzing and identifying the training "variables" characterizing work-based learning processes.

The research project, therefore stems from the awareness that the training experiences of the young people involved in the WBL pathways should be observed and studied not only and not so much in the measure of "how much" the young will learn and not only from the perspective of employability, but in particular with respect to the characteristics of the cognitive processes activated, to the relevance of changes in the relationship with knowledge, to participation in the process of constructing meanings. Basically, it is about understanding the effects of work experience on the training plan with respect to the cognitive structures of the subjects, and therefore on a long-term plan and the transferability of the willingness to learn.

It is therefore necessary to ask ourselves about some "key questions" such as: how to design new effective learning curricula for the student to facilitate school-work transitions? How can Vet Teachers enable the learner's agency for life long learning approach?

In order to study work-based learning processes, the following theoretical reference models have been identified. First of all, the category of formativity was taken from the context of Pareyson and Margiotta's thinking. For the elaboration of Taxonomy, as a pedagogical device, Tesi's work has used some relevant theoretical frameworks that are part of the broader context of constructivism: learning by doing and Experiential Learning (Dewey), construct of the practice community (Lave and Wenger), transformative learning (Mezirow) and finally the capability approach (Sen and Nussbaum).

3 Methodology

The survey required the construction of a pedagogical device called "TIQ – WBL" (Taxonomy of quality indicators in work based learning) related to the educational processes in school-work alternation paths.

Within this device I have "explored" five indicators containing each two dimensions.

Below, instead, I report the table with the Taxonomy built for empirical research:

Table 1 TIQ –WBL (Taxonomy of quality indicators of WBL)

Indicators	Dimensions	Description
1.REFLEXIVITY	<i>Self-awareness</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is the learner able to practice cognitive with regard to professional practice, including through the tutor's mediation?
	<i>Self-orientation</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is the learner able to independently elaborate development objectives of his work-based learning path with particular attention to improving his / her strengths ("professional mastery")?
2.PARTICIPATION	<i>Identity</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The learner is able to elaborate in a personal way a conscious participation in the work activities related to his learning path, configuring his identity, in different relational contexts (school, company)?
	<i>Responsability</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is the learner capable of developing "responsible" behaviors in the context of learning at work (an idea of mutual commitment, of shared values, of legitimizing one's own "membership" in the group)?
3.AGENCY	<i>Personal development</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is the learner able to identify the goals of his professional development by negotiating with the tutor, medium-long-range training objectives?
	<i>Self-efficacy</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is the learner able to develop his potential autonomously in an effective way?
4.CAPABILITY	<i>Projectuality</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is the learner able to exercise his ability to act on a project level, pursuing his / her objectives as values through negotiation with the tutor and the group?
	<i>Functionings</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can the learner develop observable skills of action in relation to the professional context that characterizes his process of learning at work?
5.GENERATIVITY		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Has the learner acquired the necessary learning to develop a consolidated and adaptable mental and professional habit for new work contexts?

4 A hypothetical framework for teacher training

The empirical-descriptive research involved the use of qualitative-quantitative tools: focus groups, interviews and self-assessment questionnaires to the actors involved in the training processes related to the case studies (students, Vet teachers).

The case study used was the alternation between school and work in some Italian technical institutes divided into two regions (Lombardy and Abruzzo).

From the analyzes present in the empirical research work, a framework emerges with respect to the lines of development of a quality training process for VET teachers oriented towards an “agency role”.

I therefore indicate, below, five educational didactic areas for VET teacher training process inspired by Taxonomy elaborated and used in the empirical survey.

Educational areas:

1. Reflexivity

Macro-objective: To enhance in the learner “the mental habit” of reflection on working practices to improve its potential and correct errors.

Micro-objectives:

- to develop a process of attention to detail in relation to the activities carried out in the learner;
- to develop in the learner the ability to monitor errors and identify strategies to avoid them;
- to make the learner understand the consequences of failure to "check for errors";
- to facilitate the self-orientation of the learner between knowledge learned in the classroom and skills, and skills learned in the workplace.

Teaching techniques: use of methodological approaches based on the pedagogical theories of reflexivity (knowledge in action) and specific teaching techniques (on-board diary, self-study, observation of working and collaborative practices), individual mentoring.

2. Participation

Macro-objective: To stimulate processes of peripheral legitimation and inclusion of single students in group situations present in working contexts.

Micro-objectives:

- To use stimulus-situations to foster shared relationships with users in work contexts without neglecting the consolidation of the different "identity codes" of the students;
- To promote the growth of the responsibility of the student in the processes of division of tasks and development of cooperative performance.

Teaching techniques: group work, mentoring techniques, didactic games, guided simulation.

3. Agency

Macro-objective: To develop in the learner a motivational orientation to the extension of his / her experiences beyond the simple execution of the task in the working area.

Micro-objectives:

- To strengthen the personal development of the learner through the lever of motivation intrinsic action;
- To experiment the advantages of an orientation to the practice that may have the motivational reinforcement value;
- To work on the lever of self-efficacy to reinforce the size related to the professional dress and skills related to the character of the young.

Teaching techniques: "autocaso", "problem de briefing and problem solving strategies".

4. Capabilities

Macro-objective: To put the learner in the conditions to release new potential outside the classroom by developing a concrete experiential experience on his ability to act and experiment specific skills in the professional context through the development of products, artefacts or results even in a real environment.

Micro-objectives:

- To understand the advantages of concrete "functioning" processes in the context of real life (for example the development of a professionalism able to organize the sale of products made, the creation of "artefacts", participation in exhibitions, events public or competition, the preparation of a promotional flyer, the design of a building using the Autocad program).
- To facilitate and guide the student's ability to act towards his own project and towards the pursuit of objectives understood as values (also towards entrepreneurial capacity).
- To accompany the student in the process of acquiring responsible judgment skills through the exercise of the narrative imagination, and of empathy (Nussbaum, 2015).

Teaching techniques: "project management" techniques, psycho-educational methodologies to support the development of the self as personalized coaching. The educational support activities can develop observable outputs, as an organization of market opportunities for the products produced, development of websites for the dissemination of commercial news on products.

5. Generativity

Macro-objective: To support the expansion of the motivational orientation of young people towards objectives of a wider spectrum than the experience of alternation or linked to individual and intersubjective aspirations.

Micro-objectives:

- Orient the young towards entrepreneurial activities (start up, for example);
- Orient the young towards forms of cooperative work in which we can develop a "leap" forward with respect to future development objectives (design a crowdfunding project, for example)

Teaching techniques: Design training (Project work techniques), practice communities with other students through virtual environments, including innovative ones (eg gamification). Analysis of entrepreneurial good practices at desk research level or through micro empirical

research with interviews and questionnaires. The project hypothesis identified above can be translated into an action plan if it becomes a shared plan between school tutors and company tutors thanks to a common action to negotiate results in terms of teaching objectives, methods and techniques used.

5 Conclusions

The capacity to act (agency) is the fulcrum of an educational project centered on the professional dimension. It is not a matter of developing professional behaviors, which are functional to the processes of adapting young people to work contexts that are already given, but of setting the conditions for development, through the strengthening of the capacity to act of young people, of a fruitful collaborative experience between business and educational institution.

Industry 4.0 scenarios will have to focus increasingly on training tools that are centered on the person, on his "mindset" and on the ability to interact in professional groups by elaborating forms of sharing and coworking. The experiences of school-work alternation and training apprenticeship are increasingly at the center of the attention of companies and the world of work.

Entrepreneurs no longer need hyperspecialists and technical experts designed to remain displaced after any technological innovation. Instead they seek young apprentices of their own work, ambitious, quick to learn, able to make decisions in the absence of complete information, to share their passions, to work in the community. Passion, mental resilience, decision making: not just skills that can be taught by writing formulas on the board.

From this point of view, the teacher as a tutor plays a decisive role in helping to "give shape" to the action of the learning subject, in order to active him to generate of new values. For example: in transferring the knowledge learned in the classroom by combining it with the technical and transversal skills; to learn by working, and to reflect while working; to relate with colleagues, with the most experienced, to share new forms of socialization within a community of practice, to take responsibility. The role of teacher in this perspective can become the main factor of expansion in the learning process of the subject, within the dual paths. The conditions for the expanding process to take place are as follows:

- The ability of teacher to model the skills to be built in the student in real contexts of learning in situation
- The ability to support group negotiation in relation to the accomplishments made
- The ability to monitor and control errors using this supervision to reinforce learning
- The ability to explore alternative ways to organize the student's learning

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Bibliographical notes

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